

SYNTHESIS OF HYDROGELS ENRICHED WITH MINERAL FERTILISERS AND INVESTIGATION OF THEIR SWELLING PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Today, global climate change and the dwindling availability of water resources are demanding the introduction of new, efficient technologies in agriculture. Under water-scarce conditions, the use of hydrogels-materials that absorb and retain water for extended periods is crucial for increasing and sustaining crop yields. At the same time, the effective use of mineral fertilisers and reducing their leaching from the soil is also a pressing issue.

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In this work, hydrogels enriched with mineral fertilisers were synthesised based on hydrolysed polyacrylonitrile (GIPAN). Ammonium polyphosphate and ammophos were incorporated into the hydrogels, and their interactions with the polymer matrix were investigated. During the hydrogel synthesis, formaldehyde was used as a crosslinking agent, forming a three-dimensional network between the polymer chains. The reaction medium's pH was maintained between 8 and 10, ensuring optimal hydrogel formation.

The main functional property of the synthesised hydrogels the degree of swelling and water retention capacity was studied experimentally. The results of the study showed that the swelling degree of the hydrogel depends on several factors, including the density of the polymer network, the amount of cross-linking agent and the concentration of mineral components.

When the effect of binder concentration on the swelling properties of the hydrogel was studied, it was found that increasing its amount from 0.1% to 0.4% enhanced its water uptake capacity. This phenomenon is explained by the formation of the polymer network and the active participation of hydrophilic groups. However, when the amount of the binder is increased to 0.6%, the polymer network becomes excessively dense, which restricts the diffusion of water molecules and consequently reduces the swelling degree.

The effect of mineral components, particularly ammonium polyphosphate, on the hydrogel properties was also studied in detail. According to the results, the optimal amount of ammonium polyphosphate was determined to be 15% (by weight of GIPAN). At this concentration, the hydrogel exhibited the highest swelling degree. The mineral components intercalate between the polymer chains, reducing crosslinking and creating a porous structure. It is precisely these voids that ensure the hydrogel's high water uptake capacity.

The swelling degree of the synthesised hydrogels was compared with that of other conventional hydrogels. The research results show that while the maximum swelling degree in plain hydrogels is 150 g/g, in ammonium phosphate-enriched hydrogels this figure reaches 175 g/g. In the hydrogels enriched with ammonium polyphosphate, the swelling degree is 195 g/g. The highest result was observed in the hydrogels enriched with both ammonium polyphosphate and ammophos, with this figure reaching up to 245 g/g.

These results indicate that the water uptake capacity of hydrogels enriched with mineral fertilisers is significantly higher than that of conventional hydrogels. Furthermore, these hydrogels have the ability to retain water over an extended period, and their application in soil allows for reduced water consumption.

Based on the above results, it was determined that the mineral fertiliser-enriched hydrogels possess high swelling capacity, good water retention properties and an effective nutrient release characteristic. Therefore, such hydrogels are considered a promising material in agriculture, enabling the efficient use of water and fertiliser resources.

References:

- 1.Ibroximov M.A., Shirinov Sh.D., Shirinova O.D. Study of synthesis and physicochemical properties of hydrogels enriched with mineral fertilizers // Science and Innovation, 2024.
- 2.Omirova R.Z., Shirinov Sh.D., Djalilov A.T. Synthesis and research of polymer hydrogels based on hydrolyzed polyacrylonitrile // Rasayan Journal of Chemistry, 2019.
- 3.Ahmed E.M. Hydrogel: Preparation, characterization, and applications // Journal of Advanced Research, 2015.
- 4.Wang C.Y. et al. Chemical Engineering Journal, 2020.
- 5.Zoratto N., Matricardi P. Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology, 2018.